

The Corporate Vision Effect on Rajabhat University Brand Building in Thailand

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Abstract—This study aims to (1) investigate the corporate vision factor influencing Rajabhat University brand building in Thailand and (2) explore influences of brand building upon Rajabhat University stakeholders' loyalty, and the research method will use mixed methods to conduct qualitative research with the quantitative research. The qualitative will approach by In-depth-interview the executive of Rathanagosin Rajabhat University group for 6 key informants and the quantitative data was collected by questionnaires distributed to stakeholder including instructors, staff, students and parents of the Rathanagosin Rajabhat University group for 400 sampling were selected by multi-stage sampling method. Data was analyzed by Structural Equation Modeling: SEM and also provide the focus group interview for confirming the model. Findings corporate vision had a direct and positive influence on Rajabhat University brand building were showed direct and positive influence on stakeholder's loyalty and stakeholder's loyalty was indirectly influenced by corporate vision through Rajabhat University brand building.

Keywords—Brand building, corporate vision, Rajabhat University, stakeholders' loyalty.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE current management of higher education in Thailand now faced with the difficulties and pressures of the various changes of outside factors such as the rapid expansion of higher education institutions. The changing forces within the educational marketplace and actively market themselves to prospective students, donors, and other constituent groups. Institutions now focus on establishing their unique places within the market by building brand identities designed to give them a distinct competitive advantage. Situation competition policy, liberalization of the educational impact of new technologies, including the results of education reform in the year 2554, however, with a variety of higher education institutions in the country educational become the commercial focus on more tactic or marketing strategy for attracting the student [1]. From such a situation, the corporate vision is very important in the service industry because vision, mission, and values are all used to provide organizational clarity and direction, which will ultimately lead to higher levels of performance and a better bottom line.

A good vision statement should emphasize a unique characteristic of the organization that differentiates it from others, and take all future activities planned for the internal

and external environment of the organization into consideration. The vision must be understood and shared by all Stakeholders of the organization. The corporate vision should help the public have an idea of the culture of the organization because the corporate vision statement should be formulated to strengthen the culture of the organization and unity and loyalty among members, and to increase employee motivation. In this sense, vision statements should reflect the organizational culture [2].

The provider is critical in reducing the risk of buying such a service, in accordance with the opinion of the loyalty is a standard of measure of the quality because of the relationship. The researchers reviewed the literature on the definition and suggested that the corporate vision associated with education is important to future brand loyalty and is related to outcomes that fostering student-to-student interaction will significantly impact alumni relationships with one another and with the institution. It was found the brand building has the effect to the loyalty of stakeholders are including repurchase, word of mouth and price sensitive that have a meaning by many scholars [3]. This cause will lead to study the corporate vision effect on Rajabhat University brand building in Thailand.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Corporate Vision Concept

Vision, mission, and values are all used to provide organizational clarity and direction, which will ultimately lead to higher levels of performance and a better bottom line. Vision, mission, and values have been the most widely used management tool over the past 20 years to motivate employees by showing them how their job fits into the grand vision and directions of the organization [4]. According to [4], vision, mission, and values have also been the least respected and most ineffectively used tools available to managers and leaders. [4] surmised that this is often the case because many leaders and employees do not know the difference between a vision, a mission, and core values, and they do not know how to implement them to create a positive influence on performance [5].

A vision is the description of a future state that an organization seeks. An example is Bill Gates's vision for Microsoft of "a computer on every desk and in every home." This vision may take years to achieve and is lofty in design, but Gates's intent for the vision is to provide a clear focus of direction. The second habit of highly effective people is to "begin with the end in mind." This is essential, what a vision

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is: It provides the end that an organization is seeking [6]. Without a vision, it is difficult for the leadership and employees to know where they are going [7].

Most companies have a vision, mission, and core values, but many do not use them effectively or at all. Studies have shown that the use of vision, mission, and values can increase the clarity of direction, as well as employee performance and morale [8]. Reported in his research on emotional intelligence and leadership styles that mission is a critical tool that authoritative leaders use. Goleman showed that the authoritative leadership style is the most effective in creating a positive work climate. McClelland described climate as including six key factors that influence an organization's working environment: flexibility, responsibility, standards, rewards, clarity, and commitment. Goleman also found that an organization's mission statement has a positive influence on the firm's innovativeness and employees' motivation. For vision, mission, or values to be used effectively requires a deliberate and planned process. First, a leader, team, or organization must discover what the organization is. A company and a team already have a vision, mission, and values; they are not created, but rather discovered, because they already exist [9]. Second, once they have been discovered, they must be communicated to all involved. This communication must ensure that the information is received, understood, and remembered, and the information must be used and talked about on a regular basis if it is to become part of the culture and a useful management tool. Last, the usage and results of the vision, mission, and values must be measured. If they are not measured, it is difficult to determine what influence they are having and how to enhance performance through the use of these tools [10].

B. Corporate Brand Building

Corporate branding strategy is a relatively new strategic initiative that is gaining popularity among the nonprofit sector as a process to manage the tensions between the claims of the hybrid identity. Corporate branding strategy is conceptualized as a dynamic process that blends organizational development and marketing techniques to highlight core competencies, seminal values, and organizational identity [11]. An important feature of a corporate branding strategy is a much deeper organizational development focus than its traditional branding counterpart, which is concerned mostly with the image of the organization. In particular, the corporate branding strategy, with its emphasis on changing stakeholder perceptions, communicating values, and enhancing organizational self-esteem is a beneficial process for the HIO in need of managing identity tensions. A hybrid identity can be advantageous during strategic initiatives such as a corporate branding strategy and the identity question, who are we, influences strategy formulation in ways not fully understood or articulated by strategists [12].

C. Stakeholder's Loyalty Concept

Even though customer satisfaction is vital to the hotel industry, customer loyalty is more precious than customer satisfaction because loyal customers will return and recommend the hotel to their friends, and this, in turn, helps increase hotel profitability. Customer loyalty is an indicator of the success of the service industry, especially the hospitality. However, customer satisfaction is not necessarily an indicator of customer loyalty [13].

By definition, customer loyalty is a consumer who intends to repurchase from the same service firms, to keep an optimistic attitude towards the service firm, and to willingly refer the service to others. Loyal customers do not switch to other service providers with small differences, such as price or service. Instead, loyal customers provide truthful and productive feedback, they combine the volume of their category purchases with the firm, they never mistreat firm employees, and they enthusiastically provide a referral to their relatives and friends [14].

Based on the academic literature, the concept of loyalty is conceptualized in four major groups. The early loyalty studies perceived loyalty as a behavioral form of repurchasing products or services. A second group measured loyalty through the part of purchases dedicated to a particular brand. A third group focused on the likelihood of purchase. Finally, some researchers integrated numerous behavioral standards in their empirical studies [15]. Customer loyalty can be categorized into two components- behavioral and attitudinal. According to Bowen and Shoemaker in 1998, behavioral dimension refers to consumers' behavior on repurchasing, which demonstrates a fondness for a service over time [16]. The customer loyalty integrates both attitudinal and behavioral components. The researchers suggested that customer loyalty is decided by a mixture of repurchase stages and relative attitude. Relative attitude is decided by strengthening and differentiating noted that the less motivation on the part of loyal customers to seek for alternatives, the more resistant they are to confront from other brands persuasively. In addition, loyal customers are more likely to recommend and advocate for the service to other customers [17].

TABLE I
 GENDER OF RESPONDENT

Genders	Frequency	Percentage
Male	155	41.0
Female	223	59.0
Total	378	100.0

III. METHODOLOGY

This research is a mixed method to conduct qualitative research with the quantitative research by using Rule of thumb [9] and provides information on a wide range of conclusions that can be applied to all areas of Thailand [21]. The statistics used for data analysis are descriptive as percentage, mean, standardization, and inferential statistics using multiple regressions by Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA),

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and Path analysis will provide. The research conceptual framework is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

TABLE II
AGE OF RESPONDENTS

Age	Frequency	Percentage
below 31 year	71	18.8
31 – 40 year	174	46.0
41 – 50 year	108	28.6
51 – 60 year	23	6.1
Above 60 year	2	.5
Total	378	100.0

TABLE III
ACADEMIC RANKS OF RESPONDENTS

Academic Ranks	Frequency	Percentage
Lecturer/Instructor	265	70.1
Assistant Professor	77	20.4
Associate Professor	29	7.7
Professor	7	1.9
Total	378	100.0

TABLE IV
EDUCATION OF RESPONDENTS

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor Degree	42	11.1
Master Degree	244	64.6
Ph.d.	92	24.3
Total	378	100.0

IV. FINDINGS

The result found reports demographic characteristics and descriptive statistics for all of the variables used in this research. Data were obtained primarily from 378 respondents of a 46-item questionnaire sent to 378 stakeholders in Rathanagosin Rajabhat University in Thailand.

The result showed that most respondents were female, 59.0 percent of 223 people and 155 of them are male and 41.0 per cent respectively. The result shows that respondents were aged 31-40 years, the number 174, representing a 46.0 percent lower last 41-50 years, 108 people, representing 28.6 percent and under 31 years of 71 people, representing 18.8 percent respectively.

The respondents have the lecturer/instructor of 265 people was 70.1 per cent, followed by assistant professor of 77

people, representing 20.4 percent and an associate professor of 29 people, representing 7.7 per cent respectively. The majority of respondents have studied the masters of 244 people, representing 64.6 percent, followed by studies at the doctoral level of 92 people, representing 24.3 per cent and education in respectively. The hypothesis testing found that Vision (VS) has a direct effect positive on corporate branding (BS), a significant statistical level .01 by the Corporate Branding (BS) influenced total. Vision (VS), which is equal to 0.550 direct effects equal to 0.550.

The hypothesis testing found that creating a corporate brand (BS) has a direct effect positively on the loyalty of stakeholders (SL), a significant statistical level .01 by the loyalty of stakeholders (SL). Influenced as well by creating a corporate brand (BS) equal to 0.875, which is equal to 0.875 direct effects. Moreover, the loyalty of stakeholders (SL) has an indirect influence on corporate vision (VS) was 0.481, which is a statistically significant influence on the level. 01.

When the index is the merging of the model showed that the model fit to the empirical data, with the index of merging the six indexes through the acceptance criteria, is the index $\chi^2/df = 1.124$, CFI = 1.000, GFI = 0.996, AGFI = 0.987, RMSEA = 0.008 and therefore concluded that SRMR = 0.007. Modeling, structural equation modeling is appropriate in harmony with the empirical data [18].

V. DISCUSSION

The study found that vision in the clarity in the University of Rajabhat is intended to highlight the importance to society and the environment is bound to be an important delivery the effect of corporate branding and sustainability [19]. The study found that key elements to create a brand that started from the vision, leadership and academic, corporate policy and university of the center of education by gathering various non-standard central elements the damming of the vision of leaders who contribute directly to the corporate branding [20]. The purpose of the study was to establish the brand and image of the brand building of Rajabhat University in Thailand. The results showed that the composition of the enterprise in terms of corporate vision in the variety of courses, convenient location of the building and producing graduates to graduate desirable of the market that affects to the branding of the institution significantly including leadership and strategy execution [22].

The effort and cost expended toward the creation of a clear institutional image are counterbalanced by the resulting increase in a student's likelihood of applying to that particular college or university. With the benefits of institutional branding outlined, the question becomes how colleges and universities are working toward building their institutional images. Recent research in this area has focused primarily on business schools, as researchers asked whether the institutions that teach the need for branding [23] was implementing those lessons themselves.

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